

25-november 2025

TEACHING THE ART OF ARGUMENTATIVE WRITING

Yunusova Nilufar Ulugbekovna

Lecturer at the English department,
University of World Economy and Diplomacy

Tashkent, Uzbekistan,

nyunusova@uwed.uz

Abstract. This article is intended to address the notion of “argument” which is used to describe the structure of many types of academic writing in English. Writers make a claim about the topic that they are writing about, and then they support their claim with evidence. Earlier many researchers discussed the elements, structure, and types of arguments in academic writing. Here, we will elucidate how to analyze other peoples’ arguments as a way to teach argumentation to students.

Keywords: academic writing, types of arguments, claim, evidence, reasoning, critical thinking.

Introduction. “The argumentative essay – the gold standard of persuasive writing – may be a better measure of good rationalization than good critical thinking” J. Southworth. It has been observed that students encounter various challenges and may require assistance with creating argumentative essays for a number of reasons. For example, these include issues with argument development, including the building of an argumentative thesis statement, the organisation or structuring of arguments, the generation and growth of arguments, and a lack of knowledge of opposing claims and counterarguments.

25-november 2025

The concept of "argument," which is used to characterise the structure of many different forms of academic writing in English, has been tried to be introduced in this article. After making a claim regarding the subject of their writing, authors provide evidence that supports up their claim. An essential component of academic writing in English is the basic claim + support structure. Appreciatively, it may be found in a variety of writing styles, so English language learners are familiar with it. When teaching, we might begin by assisting students in identifying the claim + support design.

Main part. Numerous scholars have previously examined the components, organisation, and categories of arguments in academic writing. In order to teach students about argumentation, first of all, it is better to explain them how to evaluate the arguments of others. It is essential to consider the following questions before starting reading:

- How do you know what the author's claim is?
- How can you help students identify the argument in a text?

Reading arguments often, the first step to trying something new, reviewing the work of others who have done it successfully. For students, looking at how other academic writers structured their arguments can be a helpful way to learn how arguments work. Then, students will be ready to build and revise their own arguments. Moreover, reading and writing always come together, hand in hand, and comparative analysis is an essential tool for learners with a little experience.

Over the course of my teaching career, I have been trying to implement various techniques in my academic writing classes. One of them is CER model, which is very supportive to explain students how to structure their arguments in their writings. One way to teach the CER model is to create a visual chart to represent the features of the argument found in a text. Some refer to this as an argument map because it shows how the author constructed the argument. Such a map helps students see and follow the path between the **claim**, **evidence**, and **reasoning**, and how the writer used these features. Mapping arguments

25-november 2025

is a way to apply active reading and critical thinking to analyze a text. As a teacher, we can guide students by helping them ask the right questions about the text they are analyzing. We can model for them how to look for different elements of the argument by asking specific questions. We can also show them where to look for those elements in the text. To answer these questions, as Figure 1. shows, students need to find the words, phrases, or sentences in the text that present a specific element of the argument. Following, students should work to identify the elements and then understand their answers in the text, or they can add a column in a chart like this one and copy their answers into the chart. The result will be a map of the author's argument. I've included two example argument maps below that I occasionally use with my UWED students.

Argument Map

Element	Questions to ask	Places to look
Audience	Who are the readers? Where and when was the text published?	writing style (word choice, organization, tone) Publication information
Claim	What is the writer's position, and why does it matter to the audience?	Introduction, end of the first paragraph
Background	What background knowledge do readers need to have in order to understand the argument?	Introduction Beginning of body paragraphs
Support	What evidence or examples support the claim?	Middle of body paragraphs
Reasoning	Where does the author connect the claim with the	Near the end of paragraphs Conclusion

25-november 2025

	Supporting evidence? Where does the author address other viewpoints?	
--	--	--

Figure1. Framework of the words, phrases, or sentences in the text that present a specific element of the argument.

Strategies for mapping arguments.

There are additional strategies you can use to help students analyze and then create arguments:

- **Outlining:** Students use an argument map to plan out the claim, support, background, and reasoning of their argument before they begin writing.

- **Reverse outlining:** Students create an outline of a source text by listing the main idea of each paragraph. The list of main ideas can be made into an outline that will allow them to see the connection between the points of the argument. It is a great way for them to review their own drafts for revision, too.

- **Annotation:** Students can work alone or together to highlight and/or make notes of the elements of an argument they find in the source text.

- **Text reconstruction:** Give students a text that has been split into separate sentences or paragraphs and put those into a random order. Have students organize the pieces to reconstruct the text in the correct order.

It is clear that, using multiple approaches have been considered as an effective way in teaching academic writing. The following approach connected with categorizing arguments, which includes: the audience, claim, background, support and reasoning (**Figure 2**) is also can be implemented in ESP classes. For example, **Figure 2.** shows that students may complete this task by first scanning or skimming the text. Since we have classes with students of International Relations and Political science course students, the text related to revolutions is provided as an example. First of all, students should identify and underline

25-november 2025

the arguments, and then classify every argument they have discovered. They can work in pairs or in groups to do this task.

ARGUMENT MAP

Title and author of argumentative text for analysis:

REVOLUTIONS

Feature	
Audience	<p>Readers of the political news are upper intermediate English for Specific Purposes (ESP) students.</p> <p>They are curious to learn more about politics.</p> <p>The tone of the writing is formal. A key point is stated in the title. Each paragraph's topic sentences display a clearly organized structure.</p>
Claim Thesis	<p>In the Introduction's second clause:</p> <p>Revolution is held to challenge not only the established political order but also the economic system, social structure, and the value system of those societies as proved by the greatest revolutions of European history which happened in England, France and Russia.</p>
Background Context	<p>Philosophers of ancient Greece believed that society where existed a firmly established code of beliefs could hinder the revolution</p> <p>Religious authority was so strong its beliefs in the maintenance of order so fundamental that the church required that people</p>

25-november 2025

	should accept the inequalities of power, instead of upsetting the stability of society.
Support Evidence	English poet Milton, an active participant of the English Revolution of 1640, regarded revolutionary processes as the right of society to protect itself from abusive tyrants. Immanuel Kant favoured the idea that a revolution was a natural step for a higher ethical foundation for society. Karl Marx elaborated the idea of world revolution basing on the doctrine of class struggle.
Reasoning rationale	Revolutions can alter the perceptions of the populations of the states in which they occur. The success of the revolution in Russia had a knock-on-effect that it helped inspire communist revolutionaries in other states to launch and sustain struggles against their own governments.

Figure 2. Analysis of an argumentative text.

In our academic writing classes, constructing a strong thesis statement is one of the most difficult assignments. A very simple and straightforward method of crafting persuasive thesis statements is provided in order to improve the claim section. The greatest technique to develop an ideal thesis statement, in my opinion, is to turn the prompt into a question. I used to demonstrate several bad and excellent thesis statements for my students to compare in order to teach them how to develop a strong thesis statement. However, it wasn't always successful because it was a little difficult to explain how to write them appropriately. By using questions and responses, I inspired my students to learn more about the subject. They might therefore write a more focused thesis that addresses the issue and makes an obvious claim in collaboration.

25-november 2025

Reading in particular, which was often thought of as a passive method of learning, is now one of the active ones. It's a good idea to reevaluate and analyze the texts we read on a daily basis and to look for arguments therein. Because we usually concentrate on fundamental ideas rather than arguments, this technique leaves a lasting impression on both me and my pupils. We also like the CER model and the argument map since they demonstrate how the author constructed the argument.

Conclusion. Students' understanding of arguments in academic writing has completely changed as a result of the knowledge they learnt while conducting research on producing argumentative papers. They realised that arguments are neither facts nor negative viewpoints. They have gained knowledge of argument forms and structure, how to assess arguments' characteristics, and how to create training methods for argumentative writing. The concept and characteristics of academic arguments, the audiences' expectations for academic arguments, the method for analysing arguments, and the strategies for teaching argumentation were all methodically defined.

References:

1. Yaniskaya L. K., (2020). "English for Diplomacy and Politics".
2. Schick K., & Schubert, L. So what? The Writer's Argument. New York, New York: Oxford University Press (2017).
3. Southworth J., (2020). "The problem with argumentative writing".
4. Kadyrkhodjayeva D.B., Intelligent educational systems of the present and future (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14622043>
5. Yunusova N., The role of literature in teaching English as a foreign language. Prospects of world science (2019, p.261). Materials of the XV International scientific and practical conference (July 30 - august 7, 2019) Science and Education Ltd Registered in England & Wales Registered Number: 08878342 Office 1, Velocity Tower, 10 St. Mary's Gate,

25-november 2025

Sheffield, S Yorkshire, England, S1 4lr

https://scholar.google.com/scholar?start=20&q=Yunusova+Nilufar&hl=en&as_sdt=0,5

6. Yunusova N. U. Key Concepts of Product and Process Writing. <https://proceedings-uwed.uz/> UWED, Tashkent, Uzbekistan, (2025, January 9).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14620995>

7. Yunusova Nilufar Ulugbekovna. (2024, December 11). The Challenges students may face in Academic Writing. Tashkent, Uzbekistan <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14382205>

8. Developing-and-Teaching-Academic-Writing-Courses-Spring- OPEN (2023) Section-3-2023-Jun-07_17-12-52-889.